

The Influence of Sari Ginger Drinking on the Reduction of Gravidarum Emregency Frequency in Trimester I and II Pregnant Mother in BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda in 2018

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Abstract— Pregnancy is a physiological process that almost always happens to every woman. The occurrence of pregnancy causes hormonal changes such as estrogen, progesterone, and HCG (chorionic gonadotropin). These hormones are thought to be the cause of emesis gravidarum. If emesis gravidarum is not treated properly, it can become hyperemesis gravidarum. This study aims to determine the effect of giving ginger juice drink on the reduction in the frequency of emesis gravidarum in first and second trimester pregnant women at BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda T 2018. This type of research is a research quantitative that is Pre Experimental with research design One Group Pre Test Post Test Design, which was conducted on pregnant women with emesis gravidarum. Based on statistical results using Paired T-Test was obtained p -value = 0.000 (<0.05), then H_0 is rejected it means a significant difference between the provision of ginger juice to decrease the frequency of morning sickness in pregnant women in the first and second trimester BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda 2018. So it can be concluded that there is a significant effect of giving ginger juice drinks to decrease the frequency of emesis gravidarum in first and second trimester pregnant women in BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda 2018. in first and second trimester pregnant women in BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda 2018.

Keywords— First and second trimester of pregnancy, emesis gravidarum, ginger juice drink.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pregnancy is a physiological process that almost always occurs in every woman. Pregnancy occurs due to the meeting of sperm and ovum, growing and developing in the uterus for 259 days or 37 weeks or up to 42 weeks (Nugroho and Utama, 2014). The occurrence of pregnancy causes hormonal changes in women due to an increase in the hormones estrogen, progesterone, and the release of the hormone HCG (*human chorionic gonadotropin*). These hormones are thought to be the cause of emesis gravidarum (Manuaba, 2010).

Nausea and vomiting (*Emesis Gravidarum*) is a state of nausea and vomiting that occurs during pregnancy between 4-8 weeks and continues until 14-16 weeks of pregnancy. If *emesis gravidarum* is not treated with well then it can become *hyperemesis gravidarum* which is a state of excessive nausea and vomiting in pregnancy, so as to increase the risk of pregnancy disorders. *hyperemesis gravidarum* Very pathological is very rare compared to nausea and vomiting. For that, in order not to arrive at severe conditions, it is necessary to have a good adaptation to the situation. Nausea vomiting in pregnancy has a significant impact on family life, decreases the ability to perform activities, social function and the development of stressful situations. Excessive nausea and vomiting can cause body fluids to decrease, so the blood becomes thick (*hemoconcentration*) and blood circulation to the tissues slows down. If that happens, then the consumption of oxygen and food to the tissue also decreases. Lack of oxygen and food to the tissue will cause tissue damage that can reduce maternal health and the development of the fetus it

contains. In this case serious handling is needed (Fitria, 2013).

Ginger is believed to help improve nausea and vomiting by stimulating the motility of the gastrointestinal tract, and stimulating the secretion of saliva, bile and gastric secretion products. Ginger has anti-properties and can be used by pregnant women to reduce the frequency of *emetic emesis gravidarum*. Ginger has active substances that can treat nausea and vomiting, namely *gingerols*, *shogaols*, *galanolactone*, and *terpenoids* (Rahmani, 2014). Ginger is very effective in reducing *metoclopramide*, an induction agent for nausea and vomiting. Ginger is a plant that is widely used as a spice in cooking, giving the aroma of food, drinks and ingredients of traditional medicines. Another advantage of ginger is that it is cheap and easy to reach by the public.

Based on a preliminary study conducted by researchers at BPM Eni Marfuah, in the past year from October 2016 to October 2017, 84 pregnant women had *emesis gravidarum*, and data of pregnant women who had *emesis gravidarum* during the last 3 months, August, September, October, as many as 34 pregnant women. From these data it can be concluded that the incidence of *emesis gravidarum* shows a fairly high percentage and this disorder can cause discomfort in pregnancy. Therefore, researchers are interested in researching about "The effect of giving ginger juice drinks on the reduction in the frequency of *emesis gravidarum* in first and second trimester pregnant women" so that we can find out the benefits of ginger to overcome nausea and vomiting in pregnant women, because people do not know more about the benefits ginger for pregnant women, so hopefully the public can use ginger as an alternative before using antiemetic drugs.

II. METHODS

Type of research is a research *quantitative that is Pre-Experimental* with research design *One Group Pre Test Post Test Design*, which is conducted on pregnant women with *emesis gravidarum*. In this type of research design, one group was treated and the results were observed (treatment was an independent variable and the results were the dependent variable (Arikunto, 2002).

The population in this study were all pregnant women who had *emesis gravidarum* BPM Eni Marfuah for 3 last month as many as 34 people. The number of samples was 24 respondents. The sampling technique in this study was consecutive sampling. In consecutive sampling, all subjects who came and met the selection criteria were included in the study until the number of required subjects were fulfilled. The variables in this study were divided into two categories namely Independent variables: the effect of giving ginger juice drinks and Dependent variables:

Frequency of *emesis gravidarum* in first and second trimester pregnant women. This research instrument is primary data in the form of observation sheets containing the frequency of nausea and vomiting in the first day before treatment and frequency the nausea vomiting 1 day after the respondent's treatment and filling. And secondary data are reports of pregnant women suffering from *emesis gravidarum* at BPM Eni Marfuah.

Implementation of data analysis using a computer program. analysis was *Univariate* used to obtain a description of the frequency distribution while analysis was *bivariate* used to examine the effect of ginger in reducing nausea and vomiting in pregnancy.

III. RESULTS

a. Characteristics of Respondents

This study was conducted on 24 respondents who met the study inclusion criteria. Of these 24 respondents were given ginger juice drinks for 4 days. The results of data processing will be displayed in the form of tables. The table of respondent characteristics is as follows:

TABLE 1. Frequency Distribution Based on Age Maternal

Characteristics of Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-19 Year	2	8,3%
20-35 Year	22	91,7%
TOTAL	24	100%

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 1. It is known that the age of respondents 20-35 years has the biggest presentation, which is 22 respondents (91.7%) and the age of respondents 18-19 years has the smallest presentation, namely 2 respondents (8.3%).

TABLE 2. Frequency Distribution Based on Education

Education	Frequency	Percentage
SD	3	12,5%
SMP	13	54,2%
SMA	6	25%
S1	2	8,3%
TOTAL	24	100%

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 2. It is known that the education of junior high school respondents has the highest presentation, namely 13 respondents (54.2%) and the education of S1 respondents has the smallest presentation, namely 2 respondents (8.3%).

TABLE 3. Frequency Distribution Based on Age of Pregnancy

Age of Pregnancy	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Trimester I	15	62,5%
Trimester II	9	37,5%
TOTAL	24	100%

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 3. It is known that the gestational age of the trimester respondent I has the largest presentation, which is 15 respondents (62.5%) and the gestational age of the trimester II respondent has the smallest presentation which is 9 respondents (37.5%).

TABLE 4. Frequency Distribution Based on Occupation Mother

Parity	Frequency	Percentage
A housewife	14	58,3%
private	7	29,2%
farmer	3	12,5%
TOTAL	24	100%

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 4 It is known that respondents who have jobs as housewives or mothers who do not work have the largest presentation, namely 14 respondents (58.3%) and respondents who work as farmers have the smallest presentation, namely 3 respondents (12.5%).

TABLE 5. Frequency Distribution Based on Maternal

Parity	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1	8	33%
2	10	42%
3	5	21%
4	1	4%
TOTAL	24	100%

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 5 It is known that the respondents in parity 2 had the biggest presentation, as many as 10 respondents (42%) and respondents in parity 4 had the smallest presentation, namely 1 respondent (4%).

b. Overview Gravidar Emesis

TABLE 6. Frequency Distribution of the Amount of Gravidarum Emesis Before and After Treatment

Nausea and Vomiting Range	Number of respondents	
	Before treat	After treat
Nausea & Vomiting < 5x/hari	8	23
Nausea & Vomiting 5-10x/hari	16	1
TOTAL	24	24

Source: Primary Data, 2018

Based on table 6 shows that there were 8 respondents responding before treatment with nausea and vomiting <5 times / day and 16 respondents experiencing nausea and vomiting as many as 16 respondents. After treatment, the results showed that the number of respondents who experienced nausea and vomiting <5x / day were 23

respondents and respondents who experienced nausea and vomiting 5-10x / day were 1 respondent.

c. Mean Vomiting Nausea and Vomiting Frequency Before and After Treatment

TABLE 7. Average Results Frequency of Nausea and Vomiting Before and After Treatment

Classification	Mean
Before treatment	5,92
After treatment	2,29

Source: Primary Data 2018

Based on table 7, it shows that the average of pregnant women who experience nausea and vomiting before giving treatment is 5.92 and after treatment 2.29 and the difference is 3.63 so that there is a decrease in the average value before and after treatment.

d. Consumption of Ginger Juice

Respondents were given treatment for 4 days by drinking 1 gram of ginger juice drink / day. Data analysis of 24 respondents who consumed ginger juice can be seen in table 8. The following:

TABLE 8. Respondents Who Drank Ginger Sari Beverage

Classification	Number of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Respondents who spends drink cider ginger	24	100%
Not spent drink cider ginger	0	0%

Source: Primary Data 2018

e. Effect of Ginger Juice Drinks on the Decreased Frequency of Emesis Gravidarum in Trimester I and II Pregnant Women

TABLE 9. Results of Paired T-Test Analysis Before and After Treatment

Respondent	Rata-rata	p-value
Before treatment	5,92	0,000
After treatment	2,29	

Source: Primary Data 2018

In table 9 Shows the average number of *emesis gravidarum* to the respondent before the treatment is 5.92 while the number of *emesis gravidarum* to the respondent after treatment is 2.29 and a difference of 3.63 is obtained so that there is a decrease in the average value before and after treatment. The statistical test obtained *p-value*= 0,000 or smaller than the value of α (0.05). Based on the statistical results can be concluded that significant H_0 is rejected between them means that there are significant administration ginger juice to decrease the frequency of *morning sickness* in pregnant women first and second trimester in BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda2018.

IV. DISCUSSION

a. Age on Gravidarum Emesis

The results showed the age of respondents 20-35 years had the greatest presentation of 22 respondents (91.7%) while the age of respondents 18-19 years had the smallest presentation of 2 respondents (8.3%). This means that the majority of respondents are at a productive age that is healthy and safe

(not at risk), that is, the age of 20-35 years, which at that age is the productive age. This is consistent with research conducted by Yunia on "Relationship between husband support, maternal age, and grvida." "The relationship of husband support, maternal age, and grvida to the incidence of emesis gravidarum" in 2014 which stated that most of the respondents in their study were at productive age (20-35 years).

At a healthy reproductive age most women can undergo pregnancy, childbirth and childbirth in optimal conditions so that the mother and baby are healthy (Irawan, 2009). Age 20-35 years old female reproductive organs have developed and function optimally so that it will reduce various risks during pregnancy. Conversely, age <20 years and > 35 years are more at risk of experiencing pregnancy disorders (Gunawan, 2010).

b. Education on Gravidarum Emesis

The results of the study found that respondents with junior high school education had the greatest presentation, namely as many as 13 respondents (54.2%), high school education with 6 respondents (25%), elementary school education with 3 respondents (12.5%) and the smallest presentation namely education S1 2 respondents (8.3%). This means that most respondents have junior high school education, this is in accordance with the theory which states that education is still low can increase the incidence of emesis gravidarum because they are difficult to receive modern health services and difficult to change habits, especially in the village, so they are difficult to accept educational and pregnancy information related to emesis gravidarum provided by midwives (Manuaba, 2010).

c. Gestational Age against Emesis Gravidarum

The results showed that the gestational age of respondents in the first trimester had the largest presentation, as many as 15 respondents (62.5%) and the gestational age of the second trimester had the smallest presentation, 9 respondents (37.5%). This is consistent with the theory that states that nausea and vomiting occur during the first trimester of pregnancy between 4-8 weeks and continue until the second trimester of 14-16 weeks of pregnancy (Manuaba, 2010).

d. Employment of Respondents

The results of the study showed that respondents with work as housewives or mothers who did not work had the greatest presentation of 14 people (58.3%) while mothers who worked privately were 7 respondents (29.2%) and mothers who worked as farmers have the smallest percentage, namely 3 respondents (12.5%).

This shows that most respondents have jobs as housewives. This is consistent with the theory according to (Notoatmodjo, 2007) work is something that is intentionally done for the expenditure of energy by someone in achieving certain goals. Working generally is a time-consuming activity, so pregnant women who work experience anxiety less than women who do not work because work can divert feelings of anxiety for pregnant women. Where anxiety continues to cause decreased appetite, physical weakness and nausea (Jhaquin, 2010).

e. Parity against Emesis Gravidarum

The results showed that respondents with parity 2 had the largest presentation of 10 respondents (42%) while respondents in parity 1 were 8 respondents (33%), respondents in parity 3 were 5 respondents (21%) and respondents were at parity 4 had the smallest presentation, namely 1 respondent (4%). This shows that respondents who were in parity 2 had the largest presentation.

This is not in accordance with the theory (Yunia, 2014) that emesis gravidarum is more common in primigravidas. In a woman who is pregnant for the first time, levels of progesterone and estrogen are usually higher than in subsequent pregnancies, so nausea and vomiting are more common in primigravidas. The production of the hormones estrogen and progesterone change in a woman's first pregnancy so that the amount of *oestriol* free (nausea and vomiting as a result) and will be lower in subsequent pregnancies O'Brien & Neber, 1995 (in Wesson, 2002). Most primigravida have not been able to adapt to the hormones estrogen and chorionic gonadotropin. This increase in hormones makes stomach acid levels increase, resulting in nausea (Prawirohardjo, 2008).

In this study parity 2 is still experiencing nausea, vomiting, this can be caused by other factors such as predisposing factors and psychological factors such as stress and so on (Priyanti, 2014).

f. Effect of Ginger on the Decrease of Emesis Gravidarum

From the results of research conducted at BPM Eni Marfuah Samarinda which aims to find out the effect of giving ginger juice drink on the reduction in the frequency of emesis gravidarum in first and second trimester pregnant women with a sample of 24 respondents who have met the criteria and the results obtained there is the effect of giving ginger juice drink to a decrease in frequency emesis gravidarum in first and second trimester pregnant women. The average number of emesis gravidarum before treatment was 5.92 while the number of emesis gravidarum for respondents after treatment was 2.29 and a difference of 3.63 was obtained so there was a decrease in the average value before and after treatment.

Paired T-Test results show that the p -value = 0,000 or smaller than the value of α (0.05) then there is a difference in the frequency of emesis gravidarums before and after treatment is given. This proves that after giving treatment the respondent has decreased the frequency of emesis gravidarum.

In this study, the ginger used was emprit ginger / *Zingiber officinale roscoe*. The analysis of ginger juice drink content is a content of 0.8% water content, 0.04% fiber content, 0.4% protein content and 0.03% ash content (BPTP East Kalimantan, 2018).

In this research, ginger has been proven to reduce the frequency of emesis gravidarum because ginger contains gingerol, the most important compound in ginger and has antiemetic activity that blocks serotonin, which is a messenger chemical. If this compound is blocked then the muscles of the digestive tract will relax and weaken so that nausea is reduced (Budhawaar, 2006).

The mechanism of action of ginger is known to have an

effect on gastric, increase pulse and peristalsis and antiserotonin. Ginger acts directly on the digestive tract and avoids the side effects on the central nervous system that commonly occur in antiemetic work (Basirat, Z. et al. 2009).

Spicy substances from ginger release spicy substances from sensory fibers. The spicy substance released stimulates cholinergic and histaminicneurin to release ACh and histamine to produce direct muscle contractions by activating correspondence of nausea by correspondence. This is so that after nausea is excited by the spicy substance, the nausea receptor becomes inactive and cannot be excited by the agonist. Ginger therefore inhibits anticholinergic and antihistaminic actions (Quinlan, J.D., And Hill, A. 2003).

V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of research on "The Effect of Ginger Juice Drinks on the Decrease of the Frequency of Emesis Gravidarum in Trimester I and II Pregnant Women" concluded that: The number of events of Emesis Gravidarum di BPM Eni Marfuah that is as many as 24 respondents who experienced Gravidarum Emesis, the characteristics of respondents obtained age of respondents 20 -35 years had the biggest presentation, with 22 respondents (91.7%), respondents with junior high school education had the biggest presentation namely as many as 13 respondents (54.2%), the most respondents 'gestational age, namely the first trimester gestational age were 15 respondents (62.5%), the majority of respondents' jobs were housewives as many as 14 respondents (58.3%), and parity of respondents the most is parity 2 as many as 10 respondents (42%), there is the effect of giving ginger juice drink to decrease the frequency of emesis gravidarum in first and second trimester pregnant women before and after treatment with p -value = 0,000 or smaller than α (0, 05).

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